

IDENTIFICATION AND PREVENTION OF FACTORS THAT PROVOKE DISEASES AMONG THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the protection of health among the population, one of the most important measures of which is the promotion of a healthy lifestyle. A comparative analysis of bad habits and their impact on human health is also carried out. The main focus is on the impact of ecological balance on human health.

It is better to prevent this than to cure the disease. If we take more care of our health, eat better, keep our homes and villages clean, and vaccinate our children in a timely manner, we will be able to prevent many diseases

The development of scientific and technical achievements in the XIX-XX centuries, the production of antibiotics, vaccines and many of the most powerful and complex medicines for the treatment of diseases, their numerous applications in medical practice, the development of surgical methods, one can say, led to the fact that taking into account the capabilities of the body in medicine and, ultimately, were not taken into account. Especially the numerous medical benefits in our recent past have exacerbated this situation. As a result, people have formed harmful moods, such as indifference to their own health and immortality.

But at a time when curative medicine was developing, there were also purposeful people who put forward such issues as strengthening the movement towards disease prevention, organizing life taking into account the physiological and biological laws of the human body, increasing the natural capabilities of the body, improving lifestyle and health. In the 19th century, these were S. In the 20th century - Graham, I. Jennings, R. Troll, T. Nichols, J. Jackson, S. Dots, J. Shelton, P. Bregg, K. Nisi, B. Mcfedden, K. Jeffrey, I. Tilden, Y. Nikolaev and others. It is noteworthy that these selfless people simply read and studied their proposals in the field of wellness and strengthening medicine and tried them not in a general generalization, but in their personal lives, on the body, getting rid of severe pain and drawing conclusions about the results of the recovery of many of their contemporaries.

No matter how many hospitals we build, no matter how many medical personnel we train, no matter how many medicines and medical equipment we produce, no matter how many new treatment methods are used in medical practice, no more than 8-10% can ensure human health ekanmiz. Biz is the field in which we work. what is entrusted to our health as a whole has turned out to be much more unreliable.

There is no doubt that a healthy and long life has been a long-standing dream of mankind. In this regard, the main task facing any society is the realization of this dream of humanity, that is, the creation of conditions for human health and longevity.

If we look at the ideas and proposals that guided the medicine of the ancient world and the Middle Ages in health issues, we will find out that it was mainly about increasing the personal responsibility of each person for their health. Lukmani Hakim's instructions to his son, Hippocrates' recommendations on health protection, Aristotle's 10 tips to Alexander Zulkarnain and, finally, the advice of our great compatriot Ibn Sina "to provide the human body with what it deserves and what it likes" consist mainly of tips that a person should pay attention to in his life. daily life to be healthy.

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As noted above, man has lived for a long time in a state of dependence on nature. He got everything he needed from nature. Therefore, nature was treated with caution. For many years, the study of the environment, that is, nature in general, has gradually interfered with the affairs of nature, leading to changes in the environment as a result of the use of plants, animals, water and soil. Later, the development of human consciousness, science, the construction of large, very large cities, the construction of factories became an impetus for people to make mandatory use of nature. As a result, there have been significant changes in the climate, weather, composition of water, soil, air, flora and fauna. The main environmental problems in Uzbekistan are: excessive air pollution, environmental pollution and lack of drinking water, soil salinization, reduced fertility, drying of the Aral Sea, etc. A number of measures are being implemented to eliminate such situations in our republic. It has also been established that persons who have not fulfilled their constitutional obligations related to nature protection are subject to property, administrative and even criminal liability.

Drunkenness is a terrible disaster that undermines the health of any person. As the great German Adibi Goethe noted, "humanity would be able to achieve incredible success if there were no such intoxication." Drunkenness is the basis for many ailments. Indeed, as Alloma Binayi said, "Boda is the peace that comes to everyone's mind, the mind breaks through like a step." According to research by French scientists, about 85% of children who have died and become disabled fall on fruits that appeared during the binge on grape harvest holidays. Bulgarian scientist G.F. Efremov noted that of the 23 pregnant women who consumed vodka, 15 died, and 8 gave birth to disabled children. It turns out that if a woman is engaged in constant drunkenness for 3-4 years, then the offspring will be absolutely priceless from the happiness of seeing. Abu Ali ibn Sina did not say in vain: "wine is one of the poisons." For 28 years, the French doctor Demme observed ten families in which both husband and wife were addicted to alcohol. During the same period, 57 children were born in these families, 25 of whom died before the age of one, 5 of them had seizures, 5 of them had problems collecting water in the brain and 12 of them were crazy. Only 10 were born outwardly healthy.

References:

1. Ибраимова, Х. Р. (2019). Нурллаев Руслон Рустамбекович, Артиков Икром Ахмеджанович Влияние паразитарных болезней на особенности развития туберкулеза у детей, проживающих в Хорезмской области. Наука, техника и образование, 9, 62.
2. Облокулов, А. Р., Ниязова, Т. А., Мирзажанова, Д. Б., & Нуруллаев, Р. Р. (2014). Клиническая эффективность применения экдистена при первично хроническом бруцеллезе. Инфекция иммунитет и фармакология, (3-2), 32.
3. Машарипова, Ш. С., Ибраимова, Х. Р., Нурллаев, Р. Р., & Садуллаев, С. Э. (2023). ТЕЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРИБОЛЬНИЧНЫХ ПНЕВМОНИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ НАХОДЯЩИХСЯ НА ДЛИТЕЛЬНОМ АППАРАТЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОЙ ВЕНТИЛЯЦИИ ЛЁГКИХ. Scientific Impulse, 2(16), 1172-1178.
4. Ибраимова, Х. Р., Нурллаев, Р. Р., & Артиков, И. А. (2020). ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕ ТУБЕРКУЛЕЗА В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. Наука и образование сегодня, (6-1 (53)), 83-84.
5. Ибраимова, Х. Р., Нурллаев, Р. Р., & Артиков, И. А. (2019). Влияние паразитарных болезней на особенности развития туберкулеза у детей, проживающих в Хорезмской области. Наука, техника и образование, (9 (62)), 68-72.
6. Ibraximova, H. R., Nurllayev, R. R., & Matyaqubova, O. U. (2023). KICHIK YOSHDAGI BOLALAR ORASIDA ICHAK PARAZITAR KASALLIKLARINING EPIDEMIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(15), 109-114.
7. Nurllayev, R. R., Ibadullayeva, S. S., & Yoqubov, Q. Y. (2023). KICHIK QON AYLANISH DOIRASI ARTERIYALARINING MORFOLOGIK TUZILISHI. Научный Фокус, 1(8), 463-468.
8. Sadullayev, S. E., Matyakubova, O. U., Artikov, I. A., Nurllayev, R. R., Ibadullayeva, S. S., & Yakubov, K. Y. (2023). RESULTS OF STUDIES ON THE LEVEL OF POPULATION KNOWLEDGE ABOUT PARASITIC DISEASES AND ITS PREVENTION. Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science, 1(4), 15-20.
9. Ibadullayeva, S. S., Yakubov, K. Y., Artikov, I. A., Nurllayev, R. R., & Sadullayev, S. E. (2023). CHARACTERISTICS OF PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN LYMPHOCYTIC LEUKOSIS IN CHILDREN. Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science, 1(4), 21-26.
10. Nurillaev, R. R., & Matyakubova, O. U. (2023). EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STRUCTURES OF DIARRHEAL DISEASES IN THE KHOREZM REGION. PEDAGOG, 6(2), 126-129.
11. Ibrakhimova, H. R., & Nurllayev, R. R. (2023). A METHOD FOR OBTAINING PRECIPITATING SERUMS FOR THE DETECTION OF HUMAN SEMINAL FLUID USED IN THE STUDY OF PHYSICAL EVIDENCE IN FORENSIC BIOLOGICAL LABORATORIES. World Bulletin of Management and Law, 19, 42-44.
12. Djalilovna, A. M., Nurullaev, R. R., KB, T. S. A. S., & Rakhimova, M. (2022). Chronic viral hepatitis b in women of reproductive age living in the aral sea region.
13. Юсупов, Ш. Р. (2021). НУФУРОКСАЗИД-АНТАГОНИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АКТИВНЫЙ ПРОБИОТИК НА МИКОБАКТЕРИИ ТУБЕРКУЛЕЗА. In Инновационные технологии, экономика и менеджмент в промышленности (pp. 17-21).
14. Рузибаев, Р. Ю., Юсупов, Ш. Р., & Сапаева, Ш. А. (2021). МЕРЫ ДЛЯ СНИЖЕНИЯ КОРРУПЦИИ В СФЕРЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И МЕДИЦИНЫ. In Инновационные технологии, экономика и менеджмент в промышленности (pp. 227-229).
15. Нуралиев, Н. А., Нуралиева, Х. О., & Юсупов, Ш. Р. (2014). О" Программе мер по ликвидации последствий высыхания Арала и предотвращение катастрофы экосистем в

Приаралье". Журнал теоретической и клинической медицины, (4), 43-45.

16. Юсупов, Ш. Р., Аитов, К. А., Савилов, Е. Д., Абдуллаева, Д. К., & Умиров, С. Э. (2023). Этиологическая характеристика хронических вирусных Гепатитов в хорезмской области узбекистана. Байкальский медицинский журнал, 2(2).

17. Юсупов, Ш. Р., Аскарова, Р. И., Машарипова, Ш. С., & Якубова, У. Б. (2019). Анализ факторов риска, влияющих на развитие туберкулеза у детей в Хорезмской области. Наука, техника и образование, (8 (61)), 66-72.

18. Аскарова, Р. И., & Юсупов, Ш. Р. (2023). Технологии обучения и образовательная деятельность студентов в медицинских ВУЗах. Наука, образование и культура, (1 (64)), 33-36.

19. Облоқулов, А. Р., Нарзиев, И. И., Холов, У. А., Ниязов, Г. Э., & Юсупов, Ш. Р. (2018). Особенности течения кишечного лямблиоза у взрослых. Новый день в медицине, (1), 21.

20. Аскарова, Р. И., Юсупов, Ш. Р., Хасанова, М. Ф., & Атаджанова, О. Н. (2023). Основные меры профилактики населения Приаралья от туберкулеза для детей и подростков. Проблемы современной науки и образования, (7 (185)), 42-47.

